

An Expression A Day

AEAD PDF Book

No. 1-100 / 100 entries

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Do It or You'll Miss Out

やらなきや^{そん}損！

yaranakya son!

You'll miss out if you don't do it!

Variants

- やらなきや^{そん}損！
You'll miss out if you don't do it!
- やらなければ^{そん}損！
If you don't do it, you'll miss out.
- やらないと^{そん}損！
You should do it, or you'll miss out.

Adjusted Expression

やらないと^{そん}損だ^{おも}と思います。

I think you'll miss out if you don't do it.

Example

A 「やらなきや^{そん}損！」 B 「そうだね」

A: You'll miss out if you don't do it! B: Yeah, that's true.

Notes

'Yaranakya son!' is a strong recommendation meaning that if you do not do it, you will miss a valuable chance or benefit. It does not simply say

that something is necessary; it encourages the listener by framing not doing it as a loss or a waste.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

necessity

profit and loss

strong recommendation

assertion

Tags EN

immediate grammar

daily conversation

recommendation expression

profit-and-loss expression

I'm Fed Up

もう、うんざり。

mou unzari.

I'm fed up already.

Variants

- もう、うんざり。
I'm fed up already.
- もう、うんざりだ。
I'm sick of it already.
- もう、うんざりです。
I've had enough already.

Adjusted Expression

もう、うんざりだおもと思います。

I think I'm fed up already.

Example

A 「もう、うんざり。」 B 「そうだね」

A: I'm fed up already. B: Yeah, I know.

Notes

'Mou unzari' is used when unpleasant things keep happening, or when the speaker can no longer put up with someone's behavior or a situation. It does not simply mean being tired; it includes the feeling of 'I cannot take this anymore.'

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

dissatisfaction

fatigue

sense of reaching one's limit

assertion

Tags EN

immediate grammar

emotional expression

daily conversation

dissatisfaction expression

limit expression

What a Farce

ちゃばんげき
茶番劇。

chabangeki.

What a farce.

Variants

- ^{ちゃばんげき}茶番劇だ。

What a farce.

- ^{いんちき}インチキだ。

It's a sham.

- ^{ちゃばん}とんだ茶番だ。

What a ridiculous farce.

Adjusted Expression

^{ちゃばんげき} ^{おも}
茶番劇だと思います。

I think it's a farce.

Example

A ^{ちゃばんげき}「茶番劇だ」 B 「そうだね」

A: What a farce. B: Yeah, I know.

Notes

'Chabangeki' means a farce. It is used not only when a situation is ridiculous, but also when it looks as if the script or conclusion has

already been decided and people are merely acting it out. It carries a critical sense of staged insincerity, artificiality, and lack of seriousness.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

absurd situation

evaluation as ridiculous

criticism of staged insincerity

Tags EN

immediate grammar

daily conversation

emotional expression

critical expression

staged-insincerity expression

You Have Potential

の しろ
伸び代がある。

nobishiro ga aru.

There is room for growth.

Variants

- まだ上達じょうたつする。

There is room for growth.

- まだ成長せいちょうする。

You can still improve.

- もっと上手じょうずになる。

You can get better.

Adjusted Expression

の しろ おも
伸び代があると思います。

I think there is room for growth.

Example

A 「この記録きろくだったら、まだまだ伸び代の しろがある」 B 「そうだね」

A: With this record, there is still room for growth. B: Yeah, I know.

Notes

'Nobishiro ga aru' means that there is room for further growth or improvement. It can be used to encourage someone, but it also implies that the current state is not yet complete and can still be improved.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

potential for growth

room for improvement

encouragement

indirect evaluation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

daily conversation

encouraging expression

evaluation expression

room-for-improvement expression

I Can't Handle Hot Food

ねこじた
猫舌。

nekojita.

I can't handle hot food or drinks.

Variants

- ^{あつ}熱いものは^{にがて}苦手だ。
I can't handle hot food.
- ^{すこ}少し^さ冷めてからでないと^{むり}無理だ。
I can't drink hot drinks.
- I need it to cool down first.

Adjusted Expression

^{あつ}熱いものは^{にがて}苦手だと思^{おも}います。

I think I can't handle hot food or drinks.

Example

A 「^{ねこじた}猫舌だから、^{あつ}熱いのはちょっと」 B 「じゃ、^あアイスにする？」

A: I can't handle hot things, so hot food is a bit... B: Then, how about something cold?

Notes

'Nekojita' means that someone has trouble eating or drinking things when they are hot. English does not usually have a single everyday word

that directly corresponds to it, so it is often explained as "I can't handle hot food or drinks" or "I need it to cool down first."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

dislike hot food or drinks

cannot comfortably eat or drink hot things

prefer to avoid hot things

self-explanation in a dining situation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

daily conversation

food expression

bodily-sensation expression

self-explanation expression

Reservation

ご予約

Go-yoyaku

reservation

Variants

- 予約願います。

I would like to make a reservation.

- 予約をお願いします。

I would like to make a reservation, please.

Adjusted Expression

予約をお願いします。

I would like to make a reservation, please.

Example

本日はご予約のお客様のみの営業とさせていただきます。

Today, we are open only to customers with reservations.

Notes

"Honjitsu wa go-yoyaku no okyakusama nomi no eigyou to sasete itadakimasu" is a notice used in restaurants and similar settings to say that service is limited to customers with reservations. Some restaurants display this notice regularly. Even so, whether a walk-in customer who has come all the way to the restaurant is actually turned away may depend on the restaurant's practice and the situation at that moment.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

I want to make a reservation.

I would like to make a reservation, please.

I would like to make a reservation.

Tags EN

expression

daily conversation

service industry expression

Taking the Best Parts

いいとこどり

Ii-toko-dori

taking only the best parts

Variants

- とかい いなか 都会と田舎のいいとこどり。

It takes the best parts of both city life and country life.

- しごと 仕事のいいとこどりをする。

I take only the best parts of my job.

- みせ やす おい この店は安いし、美味しいし、(いいとこどり)だね。

This restaurant is cheap, delicious, and it takes only the best parts.

Adjusted Expression

そうほう りてん どうじ と い 双方の利点を同時に取り入れました。

I took the advantages of both at the same time.

Example

とかい いなか 都会と田舎のいいとこどり。

It takes the best parts of both city life and country life.

Notes

This expression refers to taking or enjoying only the most favorable parts of something. It can be used positively, as in combining advantages, or critically, as in taking only what suits oneself.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

to take only the best parts

to live a life that takes only the best parts

This restaurant takes only the best parts.

Tags EN

expression

daily conversation

praising expression

critical expression

No Verb, Still a Sentence

なか
お腹、いっぱい。

Onaka, ippai.

I'm full.

Variants

- もう、いっぱい。

I'm full already.

- 食べられない。

I can't eat any more.

Adjusted Expression

もうこれ以上は食べられません。

I can't eat any more.

Example

なか
お腹、いっぱい。

I'm full.

Notes

"Onaka, ippai" consists of just two parts, "onaka" and "ippai," and yet it functions as a complete utterance. Even without a verb, it is understood as a full sentence in context, and Japanese has many expressions of this kind.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

I'm full.

I can't eat any more.

I'm full already.

Tags EN

expression

daily conversation

food expression

expression without verb

Don't Do That

するな！

Suru na!

Don't do that!

Variants

- やるな！
Don't do it!
- するなよ！
Don't do that, okay?
- やるなってば！
I said, don't do that!

Adjusted Expression

そのような行為は禁止こうい きんしされています。

Such behavior is prohibited.

Example

するな！

Don't do that!

Notes

'Suru na!' is a strong expression used to stop someone from doing something. It consists of 'suru' followed by the prohibitive particle 'na'. It sounds very direct and forceful, and in everyday conversation it can express anger, warning, or strong restraint.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

Explanation of prohibition

Warning of prohibition

Emphasis of prohibition

Tags EN

expression

daily conversation

prohibition expression

imperative expression

Choice or Sentakushi

ちよいす せんたくし
チョイス or 選択肢

Choisu or sentaku-shi

choice or option

Variants

- 選択肢せんたくしがいくつかいくつかあって、..
There are several options for that, ...
- そういう選択肢せんたくしがあって、..
There are such options, ...
- いくつかえら選べて、..
There are several choices, ...

Adjusted Expression

いくつかせんたくし選択肢えらから、お選べびできます。

You can choose from several options.

Example

ええ、それにはいくつかせんたくし選択肢えらがあって、..

Yes, there are several options for that, ...

Notes

'Choisu' comes from English 'choice' and is used in Japanese with meanings close to 'selection' or 'option.' However, 'choisu' sounds somewhat casual, while 'sentakushi' is easier to use in explanations or

guidance. Having fixed phrases such as 'ikutsuka sentakushi ga atte, ...' makes it easier to present available options naturally in Japanese.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

Presenting options

Explaining options

Suggesting options

Tags EN

expression

daily conversation

option expression

suggestion expression

Verb-ta / Adj-i / Adj-na + koto ni

おどろいたことに、 ...

Odoroita koto ni, ...

surprisingly, ...

Variants

- おもしろいことに、 ...

Interestingly, ...

- うれしいことに、 ...

Fortunately, ...

- 残念なことに、 ...

Unfortunately, ...

Adjusted Expression

おどろ じじつ い
驚きの事実とでも言いましょうか、

How can I say it? It's a surprising fact that ...

Example

おどろ かれ にほんじん にほんご はな
驚いたことに、彼は日本人なみに日本語を話す。

Surprisingly, he speaks Japanese almost as well as a native Japanese speaker.

Notes

The pattern "verb-ta / adjective-i / adjective-na + koto ni" is used to add the speaker's evaluative comment at the beginning of a sentence.

Expressions such as "omoshiroi koto ni" and "odoroita koto ni" work like

sentence adverbs such as "interestingly" or "surprisingly." Here, "koto" is a nominal element, and the whole pattern presents the speaker's reaction or viewpoint toward what follows.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

Expression of evaluation

Expression of viewpoint

Expression of reaction

Tags EN

expression

daily conversation

expression of evaluation

expression of viewpoint

expression of reaction

Top-Class

いちりゅう
一流

ichiryu

top-class

Variants

いちりゅう
● 一流

top-class

さいこうい
● 最高位

the highest level

とっぷくらす
● トップクラス

first-rate

Adjusted Expression

いちりゅう りょうりにん
一流の料理人

a top-class chef

Example

なかむら いちりゅう りょうりにん
中村さんは一流の料理人です。

Mr. Nakamura is a top-class chef.

Notes

The word "ichi-ryu" means "top-class," "first-rate," or "of the highest level." It is used to describe a person, skill, product, or performance that is regarded as outstanding in its field.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

Evaluation of a person

Evaluation of skill

Evaluation of product

Evaluation of performance

Tags EN

expression

daily conversation

evaluation

top-class

the highest level

Doing One's Best

いっしょけんめい
一所懸命

isshokenmei

doing one's very best

Variants

いっしょけんめい
● 一所懸命

doing one's very best

ぜんりょく
● 全力で

with all one's effort

せいいつぱい
● 精一杯

to the best of one's ability

Adjusted Expression

いっしょけんめい べんきょう
一所懸命に勉強する

to study with all one's effort

Example

いっしょけんめい
一所懸命、がんばります。

I will do my very best.

Notes

The expression "issho-kemmei" means to do something with all one's effort. Historically, it literally referred to staking one's life on a single

place or holding, but in modern Japanese it is commonly used to mean "doing one's very best" or "working as hard as possible."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

Expression to indicate doing something with all one's effort

Expression to indicate effort and hard work

Expression to indicate attitude towards work or study

Tags EN

expression

daily conversation

expression of effort

expression of hard work

expression of attitude towards work or study

Everything, All of It

いっさいがっさい
一切合財

issaigassai

everything, all of it

Variants

- なんでもかんでも
everything
- ありとあらゆる
all of it
- なにもかも
the whole nine yards

Adjusted Expression

とりあえず、かんが考えられるものをすべて取りまとめて、たいおう対応します。

For now, we will gather together everything that can be considered and deal with it as a whole.

Example

いっさいがっさい一切合財、まとめてこちらでお引き受けします。

We will handle everything here, all together.

Notes

"Issai-gassai" means "everything" or "all of it," with nothing left out. It often has a slightly emphatic tone and can sound somewhat old-

fashioned or stylistically marked compared with neutral everyday expressions. Related expressions such as "nandemo-kandemo" and "ari to arayuru" are similar, but their tone and usage are not exactly the same.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

- inclusion
- emphasis
- offering service

Tags EN

- lexical expression
- inclusive expression
- emphatic expression

A Once-in-a-Lifetime Encounter

いちごいちえ
一期一会

ichigoichie

a once-in-a-lifetime encounter

Variants

- ^{いっしょう}一生に^{いちど}一度
once in a lifetime
- またとない^{であ}出会い
a unique encounter
- a meeting that comes only once

Adjusted Expression

^{いっしょう}一生に^{いちど}一度しか^{であ}ない^{たいせつ}出会い^{おも}として、大切にしたいと思います。

I would like to cherish it as a once-in-a-lifetime encounter.

Example

^{いちごいちえ}一期一会^{たいせつ}を大切に^{おも}したいと思います。

I would like to cherish this once-in-a-lifetime encounter.

Notes

'Ichigo-ichie' refers to a once-in-a-lifetime encounter, or to the idea of cherishing a moment because it will never occur in exactly the same way again. 'Ichigo' refers to one lifetime or a single occasion, and 'ichie' refers

to one meeting or gathering. The phrase is also used in the Japanese title of the film 'Forrest Gump/Ichigo Ichie', starring Tom Hanks.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

valuation

expressing preciousness

expression of encounter

Tags EN

lexical expression

value expression

expression of encounter

My Top Pick

いちお
一推し

ichioshi

top pick

Variants

- おすすめ
recommendation
- 特におすすめ
top recommendation
- お推し
favorite pick

Adjusted Expression

ことし もっと えいが
今年、最もおすすめしたい映画はこれです。

This is the movie I most highly recommend this year.

Example

ことし いちお えいが
今年一推しの映画はこれだ。

This is my top movie pick of the year.

Notes

'Ichi-oshi' refers to the item or person that the speaker most strongly recommends within a certain range. 'Ichi' means 'number one' or 'first', and 'oshi' is related to 'osu', meaning to recommend or support. 'Ichi-oshi'

does not necessarily mean objectively the best; it means the speaker's top recommendation or strongest favorite.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

recommendation

evaluation

emphasis

Tags EN

lexical expression

recommendation expression

evaluative expression

All or Nothing

いち ばち
一か八か

ichi ka bachi ka

all or nothing

Variants

- ^{うん てん まか}運を天に任せる

take a gamble

- ^{か で}賭けに出る

leave it to chance

-

go all in

Adjusted Expression

^{せいこう ほうしょう}成功する保証はありませんが、^{おも き}思い切ってやってみましょう。

There is no guarantee of success, but let's take a chance and try it.

Example

^{いち ばち}一か八かやってみよう。

Let's take a chance and try it.

Notes

"Ichi ka bachi ka" is an expression used when someone decides to take a risky chance without knowing whether the result will be a great success

or a total failure. It is often associated with gambling in tone or background, and it conveys a do-or-die attitude.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

decision

risk

challenge

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

gambling-related expression

decision expression

Rome Wasn't Built in a Day

ろーま いちにち な
ローマは一日にして成らず

roma wa ichinichi ni shite narazu

Rome wasn't built in a day.

Variants

- おお大きなことを成しな遂とげるには、じかん時間がかかります。

Great things take time to achieve.

- せんり千里の道もみち一いっ歩ぽから

A journey of a thousand miles begins with a single step.

- いし石の上にもうえ三さん年ねん

Perseverance pays off.

-

Patience and perseverance bring results.

Adjusted Expression

おお大きなことを成しな遂とげるには、じかん時間がかかります。

Great things take time to achieve.

Example

ろーま いちにち な どりよく努力とにんたい忍耐がひつよう必要です。

Rome wasn't built in a day. It takes effort and patience.

Notes

This is a well-known proverb meaning that great things cannot be accomplished quickly. It is used to remind someone that important work, growth, or achievement takes time.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

lesson

encouragement

sense of time

Tags EN

proverb

expression of effort

expression of time

Happy Birthday!

たんじょうび
お誕生日、おめでとう！

otanjoubi omedetou!

Happy Birthday!

Variants

- お誕生日、おめでとう！
Happy Birthday!
- お誕生日おめでとう！
Happy birthday!
- 誕生日おめでとう！
Happy birthday to you!

Adjusted Expression

たんじょうび
お誕生日、おめでとうございます。

Happy birthday.

Notes

The word "o-tanjoubi" means "birthday." "O" is a polite prefix. The word "omedetou" means "congratulations" and is used to celebrate a special occasion.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

celebrating someone's birthday expressing congratulations a friendly greeting

Tags EN

immediate grammar

formulaic expression

greeting expression

congratulatory expression

colloquial

Thanks, Crocodile!

どうも、^{くろこだいる}クロコダイル!

doumo, kurokodairu!

Thanks, crocodile!

Variants

- どうも、^{ありげーたー}アリゲーター!

Thanks, alligator!

- どうも、^{くろこだいる}クロコダイル!

Thanks, crocodile!

Adjusted Expression

「ありがとう」と言おうとして、まちがって「クロコダイル」と言ってしまいました。

I tried to say "arigatou" but mistakenly said "crocodile."

Example

「ありがとう」と言おうとして、「^{くろこだいる}クロコダイル」って言っちゃった

I tried to say arigatou but ended up saying crocodile.

Notes

This expression is used humorously as a mistaken or playful substitute for "arigatou." In the anecdote behind it, someone tried to remember "arigatou" by linking it to a similar-sounding English word such as "alligator," but ended up saying "crocodile" instead. The point is not correctness but the amusing sound association across languages.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

gratitude humor sound-based association

Tags EN

immediate grammar humorous expression sound association speech mistake
observational record

You're Speaking Too Fast

はやくち き と
早口で聞き取れない

Hayakuchi de kikitorenai

I can't catch what you're saying because you're speaking too fast.

Variants

- はやくち 早口でわからない

I can't follow you because you're talking too fast.

- はや 早すぎて き と 聞き取れない

You're speaking too fast for me to catch it.

Adjusted Expression

すこ 少し はやくち 早口なので、き と 聞き取れませんでした。

I could not catch what you are saying because you are speaking a little too fast.

Example

A 「昨日の映画、どうだった？」 B 「早口で聞き取れないところもあったけど、面白かったよ」

A: How was the movie yesterday? B: There were parts I couldn't catch because the speech was too fast, but it was interesting.

Notes

"Hayakuchi" refers to speaking quickly or in rapid speech. "Kikitorenai" means that the listener cannot catch or make out what is being said. The

whole expression is used when someone is speaking so fast that the listener cannot follow the speech clearly.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

asking for repetition

difficulty in understanding

adjusting conversation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

listening-comprehension expression

conversation-adjustment expression

Making Rice Balls

おにぎりを握る^{にぎ}

Onigiri wo nigiru

to make rice balls

Variants

- おにぎりを作る^{つく}
to make rice balls
- おむすびを握る^{にぎ}
to make onigiri
- to shape rice into rice balls

Adjusted Expression

炊いたご飯^たを握^{はん}って、おにぎり^{にぎ}を作^{つく}ります。

We make rice balls by shaping cooked rice with our hands.

Example

A 「おにぎり^{にぎ}を握^{たの}るのは、楽しいね！」 B 「うん、炊いたご飯^たを握^{はん}って、おにぎり^{にぎ}を作^{つく}るのは、面白^{おもしろ}いよね！」

A: Making rice balls is fun! B: Yes, shaping cooked rice into rice balls is interesting!

Notes

"Onigiri" means a rice ball, usually made by shaping cooked rice into a round or triangular form. "Nigiru" means to hold or press something in the hand, and in "onigiri wo nigiru" it describes the action of shaping rice by hand to make an onigiri. Onigiri is a popular Japanese food, often wrapped with seaweed.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

cooking

expression of action

expression of food

Tags EN

lexical expression

cooking expression

food expression

Making Omurice

おむらいす つく
オムライスを作る

Omuraisu wo tsukuru

to make omurice

Variants

- おむらいす つく
オムライスを作ります

to make omurice

- たまご つつ
卵で包んだケチャップライスを作る

to make ketchup rice wrapped in a thin omelet

-

to make an omelet-wrapped rice dish

Adjusted Expression

けちやっぷらいす うす たまご つつ おむらいす つく
ケチャップライスを薄い卵で包んで、オムライスを作ります。

We make omurice by wrapping ketchup rice in a thin omelet.

Example

A 「おむらいす た
オムライス、食べたい？」 B 「うん、大好き！」
だいす

A: Do you want to eat omurice? B: Yes, I love it!

Notes

'Omuraisu' is a Japanese-style food name made from 'omelet' and 'rice.' It refers to ketchup-flavored rice wrapped in a thin omelet, and it is a popular dish in Japan. Many international students who come to Japan

for the first time tend to enjoy omurice. Its characteristic appeal is the combination of slightly sweet egg and ketchup rice.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

cooking

expression of action

expression of food

Tags EN

lexical expression

cooking expression

food expression

Making Okonomiyaki

この や つく お好み焼きを作る

Okonomiyaki wo tsukuru

to make okonomiyaki

Variants

- この や つく
お好み焼きを作ります
to make okonomiyaki
- この や や
お好み焼きを焼く
to cook okonomiyaki
- to make a Japanese savory pancake

Adjusted Expression

こむぎこ たまご ま この や つく
小麦粉、卵、キャベツなどを混ぜて、お好み焼きを作ります。

We make okonomiyaki by mixing flour, eggs, cabbage, and other ingredients and cooking it on a hot plate.

Example

A 「この や や、食べたい？」 B 「うん、大好き！」

A: Do you want to eat okonomiyaki? B: Yes, I love it!

Notes

"Okonomiyaki" is a popular Japanese dish made by mixing flour, eggs, cabbage, and other ingredients and cooking the mixture on a hot plate.

"Okonomi" refers to what one likes or prefers, and "yaki" refers to something grilled or cooked. There are several regional styles, especially Osaka style and Hiroshima style. When I was a child, I loved eating okonomiyaki. Back then, okonomiyaki was not as glamorous as it is today. It was a simple thin pancake-like food made with flour, a small amount of cabbage, and a slice of pork. If yakisoba was included, only a few relatively well-off children could afford it. Okonomiyaki was cooked by neighborhood housewives in temporary garage-like spaces.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

cooking expression of action expression of food

Tags EN

lexical expression cooking expression food expression

Excuse Me / I'm Sorry

すみません。

Sumimasen.

Excuse me. / I'm sorry.

Variants

- すいません。

Excuse me.

- もう わけ申し訳ありません。

I'm sorry.

- しつれい失礼します。

Pardon me.

Adjusted Expression

もう わけ申し訳ありません。

I sincerely apologize.

Example

すみません、ちょっとおし教えてください。

Excuse me, could you tell me something?

Notes

'Sumimasen' is a versatile fixed expression used in many situations. It is used not only for apologizing, but also for getting someone's attention, asking for help, or beginning a request. It often works as a preface when

the speaker is about to take a little of the listener's attention or time, as in 'sumimasen, chotto oshiete kudasai'.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

apology

getting attention

request

calling for attention

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

formulaic expression

polite expression

Before a Meal

いただきます。

Itadakimasu.

Thank you for the food.

Variants

- それでは、いただきます。
Thank you for the meal.
- ありがたくいただきます。
Let's eat.

Adjusted Expression

それでは、ありがたくいただきます。

Well then, thank you for the food.

Example

食べる^た前に^{まえ}「いただきます」と^い言う。

Before eating, people say, Itadakimasu.

Notes

"Itadakimasu" is a fixed expression said before eating in Japan. It is used to begin a meal with a sense of gratitude and respectful receiving, rather than as a simple literal statement. Although the verb behind it is the humble form "itadaku," in actual use it functions as a formulaic mealtime expression.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

starting a meal

gratitude

formulaic greeting

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

formulaic expression

meal expression

Good Night

やす
お休みなさい。

oyasumi nasai.

Good night.

Variants

- お休み。
Good night.
- では、お休みなさい。
Sleep well.

Adjusted Expression

それでは、どうぞお休みください。

Well then, please have a good rest.

Example

もう遅いので、お休みなさい。

It's getting late, so good night.

Notes

'Oyasumi nasai' is a fixed greeting used before going to sleep or when parting from someone at night. It is based on 'yasumu', meaning 'to rest', with the polite prefix 'o' and the form 'nasai'. In actual use, however, it functions less as a command and more as a bedtime or nighttime parting expression. With close people, the shorter form 'oyasumi' is also common.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

greeting

expression before sleep

parting expression

Tags EN

formulaic expression

spoken

greeting expression

parting expression

Sorry to Keep You Waiting

お^ま待たせしました。

Omatase shimashita.

Sorry to keep you waiting.

Variants

- お^ま待たせいたしました。
Sorry to have kept you waiting.
- お^ま待たせしてすみません。
Thank you for waiting.

Adjusted Expression

お^ま待たせして^{もう}申し^{わけ}ありません。

I apologize for keeping you waiting.

Example

お^ま待たせしました。こちらへどうぞ。

Sorry to keep you waiting. This way, please.

Notes

"Omatase shimashita" is a fixed expression used after keeping someone waiting. Formally, it contains several layers, including the polite prefix "o", the causative verb "mataseru", "suru", the polite form "masu", and the past marker "ta", so it becomes quite complex if analyzed. In actual use, however, it is best learned as one formulaic expression meaning

"Sorry to have kept you waiting." It is often used in customer service or when resuming an interaction.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

apology customer service resuming interaction

Tags EN

immediate grammar formulaic expression polite expression apology expression

That Was Rude of Me

しつれい
失礼しました。

shitsurei shimashita.

I'm sorry. / That was rude of me.

Variants

• しつれい
失礼しました。

I'm sorry.

• しつれい
失礼いたしました。

That was rude of me.

• さっきはしつれい
失礼しました。

Sorry about that.

Adjusted Expression

さき しつれい
先ほどは失礼いたしました。

I apologize for my rudeness earlier.

Example

さっきはしつれい
失礼しました。

I'm sorry about earlier.

Notes

'Shitsurei shimashita' is a polite apology used when the speaker feels that their behavior or words were rude, inappropriate, or slightly lacking in courtesy. 'Shitsurei' means rudeness or a lack of proper manners, and

'shimashita' is the past form of 'suru', but in actual use the whole phrase functions as a fixed expression. It can be used to apologize gently for something said or done earlier, as in 'sakki wa shitsurei shimashita'.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

apology

politeness

adjusting interaction

Tags EN

immediate grammar

formulaic expression

polite expression

apology expression

Wonderful!

すばらしい！

Subarashii!

Wonderful!

Variants

- すばらしいですね。
Wonderful!
- ほんとうにすばらしい！
Excellent!
- みごとだ。
That's amazing!

Adjusted Expression

たいへんすばらしいと^{おも}います。

I think it is truly wonderful.

Example

すばらしい！よくできました。

Wonderful! You did very well.

Notes

"Subarashii" is used to express strong praise or admiration. It can be used for a performance, an idea, a piece of work, or a person's action, and in immediate use it often comes out as a direct exclamation.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

praise

admiration

evaluation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

evaluative expression

emotional expression

It's Already Bought and Ready

それは、もう買^かってある。

Sore wa, mou katte aru.

It's already bought and ready.

Variants

- もう買^かってあるよ。
I've already bought it.
- それは先に買^かってあります。
It's already been bought.
- I've already got it ready.

Adjusted Expression

それは、すでに購^{こうにゆう}入してあります。

It has already been purchased and prepared.

Example

牛乳^{ぎゅうにゆう}はもう買^かってあるから、今日^{きょう}は買^かわなくていいよ。

The milk has already been bought, so you don't need to buy it today.

Notes

The phrase "katte aru" indicates that something has already been done and is prepared. The word "katte" is the te-form of the verb "kau" which means "to buy." The word "aru" is the verb "aru" which means "to exist."

As a result of the action of the verb, something already exists. Therefore, it means "I don't have to buy it anymore" or "it's already prepared."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

completion of preparation

reassurance

confirmation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

preparation-completed expression

result-state expression

Shall I Get One?

じゃ、それ、ひとつ、^か買っておきましょうか。

Ja, sore, hitotsu, katte okimashou ka.

Well then, shall I get one?

Variants

- じゃ、それ、^か買っておきましょうか。

Well then, shall I buy one?

- ^{さき}先に^か買っておきましょうか。

Shall I get one in advance?

-

Shall I pick one up for later?

Adjusted Expression

では、それをひとつ^か買っておきましょうか。

Well then, shall I buy one in advance?

Example

^{あと}後^{ひつよう}で必要かもしれないから、じゃ、それ、ひとつ、^か買っておきましょうか。

We might need it later, so well then, shall I get one?

Notes

"Katte okimashou ka" is used to suggest buying something. "Katte" is the te-form of the verb "kau" which means "to buy." "Okimashou ka" is the

polite form of the verb "oku" which means "to do" or "to prepare." It is easy to understand that when expressing something that has already been bought as a preparation, "te aru" is used, and when buying something for preparation, "te oku" is used.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

offering preparation suggestion

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken offering expression preparation expression

Like Two Peas in a Pod

うりふた
瓜二つ

Uri futatsu

like two peas in a pod

Variants

- そっくり
exactly alike
- 生き写し^{うっ}
almost identical
- よく似ている^に
look just the same

Adjusted Expression

ふたり^みわ^に
二人は見分けがつかないほどよく似ています。

The two are so alike that it is hard to tell them apart.

Example

ふたり^{うりふた}
二人はまるで瓜二つ。

The two are just like two peas in a pod.

Notes

"Uri futatsu" is an idiomatic expression meaning that two people look so similar that it is hard to tell them apart. "Uri" refers to a melon or gourd-like fruit, and the expression compares two similar-looking people to two

similar gourds placed side by side. It is mainly used for resemblance in appearance.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expression of resemblance

evaluation

observation

Tags EN

lexical expression

resemblance expression

idiomatic expression

Shall We Have Some Tea?

お^{ちゃ}茶しませんか。

Ocha shimasen ka.

Shall we have some tea?

Variants

- ちょっとお^{ちゃ}茶しませんか。
How about some tea?
- お^{ちゃ}茶でもしませんか。
Would you like to have tea?
- お^{ちゃ}茶しない？
How about a tea break?

Adjusted Expression

もしよろしければ、お^{ちゃ}茶でも飲^のみませんか。

If you like, would you like to have some tea or something to drink?

Example

すこ^{すこ}やす^{やす}みたいですね。お^{ちゃ}茶しませんか。

It looks like we could use a little break. Shall we have some tea?

Notes

"Ocha" literally means "tea," but here it works as a typical example of something to drink during a break. It can imply taking a short break, having something to drink, or starting a conversation. "Shimasen ka" is

formally a polite negative question, but in this expression it functions as an invitation rather than a negative statement. The particle "ka" marks a question, but in casual speech it can be omitted, as in "ocha shinai?" Just because the word is "ocha," it does not mean that you cannot drink coffee.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

invitation

taking a break

starting a conversation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

invitation expression

break-time expression

When you are called your name

なあに？

naani?

What?

Variants

- なに？

What?

- なあに

Yes?

- なに？ どうしたの？

What is it?

Adjusted Expression

なに よう
何かご用ですか。

Do you need me for something?

Example

A 「たなか田中くん！」 B 「なあに？」

A: Tanaka! B: What?

Notes

"Naani" is a colloquial expression close to "What?" or "What is it?" It can be used when someone calls your name or seems to want to say something to you. It often sounds soft and familiar, so in more formal

situations expressions such as "nan deshou ka" or "nanika goyou desu ka" are more appropriate.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

response to being called

checking

starting interaction

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

response-to-being-called expression

Excellent

すごい！

sugoi!

Excellent!

Variants

- すごい！
Excellent!
- すごいですね。
Amazing!
- すごいなあ。
Great!

Adjusted Expression

それはたいへんすばらしいとおもいます。

I think that is excellent.

Example

A 「これなら満足？」 B 「うん！本当にすごいよ！」

A: Is this satisfactory? B: Yes! It's really excellent!

Notes

"Sugoi" is a colloquial expression used to show surprise, admiration, or praise. It can be used for a person, action, result, or event when the speaker feels that something is extraordinary, intense, or strongly

impressive. It is often positive, but depending on the context it can also simply express a high degree or intensity.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

admiration

praise

surprise

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

emotional expression

evaluative expression

Lovely!

すてき！

Suteki!

Lovely!

Variants

- すてきですね。
Lovely!
- ほんとうにすてき！
That's lovely!
- すてきだね。
How nice!

Adjusted Expression

とてもすてきだおもと思います。

I think it is very lovely.

Example

その服ふく、すてき！

That outfit is lovely!

Notes

"Suteki" is used to express warm admiration or a favorable impression. Compared with "subarashii," it often sounds lighter, softer, and more personal, and it is frequently used for appearance, atmosphere, taste, or small moments that feel charming.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

praise

admiration

positive evaluation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

evaluative expression

emotional expression

You Know What?

あのね？

Ano ne?

You know what?

Variants

- あのね、
You know what?
- あのさ、
Hey, listen.
- ねえ、あのね。
So, you know...

Adjusted Expression

あのですね、ちょっとお話し^{はな}したいことがあります。

Well, there is something I would like to tell you.

Example

あのね、きょう学校^{がっこう}でね、おもしろいことがあったんだ。

You know what? Something interesting happened at school today.

Notes

"Ano ne" is a casual expression used to draw the listener in before saying something. Rather than simply seeking agreement, it often works as a soft way to begin speaking, especially when the speaker wants attention, wants to share something personal, or is about to tell a small story.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

calling someone

starting to speak

directing attention

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

speech-opening expression

attention-directing expression

Everything

ぜんぶ

Zenbu

everything

Variants

- ^{ぜんぶ}全部
everything
- すべて
all of it
- ^{なに}何もかも
the whole thing

Adjusted Expression

^{かんけい}関係するものを、^{ぜんぶ}全部まとめて^{ふく}含みます。

It includes everything related, all together.

Example

これ、ぜんぶ^た食べていいの？

Can I eat all of this?

Notes

"Zenbu" means "everything," "all," or "the whole thing." It is a very common everyday word used to refer to the whole of something. Compared with "subete," it often sounds more casual and more natural in conversation.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

inclusion emphasis referring to the whole

Tags EN

lexical expression inclusive expression spoken

No Way!

ありえん！

arien!

No way!

Variants

- ありえない！
No way!
- そんなのありえん！
That's impossible!
- まさか！
Unbelievable!

Adjusted Expression

それは、ありえない^{おも}と思います。

I think that is impossible.

Example

3回連続^かでジャンケン^{じゃんけん}で勝^かった？ ありえん！

Notes

"Arien" is a casual spoken form of "arienai." It expresses strong disbelief, surprise, or the feeling that something is hard to believe. Rather than sounding like a careful judgment, it often works as a quick reaction close to "No way!" or "Unbelievable!"

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

disbelief

surprise

strong denial

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

emotional expression

disbelief expression

Oh, Really?

へえー

Hee

Oh, really?

Variants

- へえ。
Oh, really?
- へえー。
Wow.
- へえ、そうなんだ。
Is that so?

Adjusted Expression

そうなんですか。

Oh, is that so?

Example

A 「その人、20か国語話せるんだって」 B 「へえー」

A: They say that person can speak twenty languages. B: Oh, really?

Notes

"Hee" is an interjection used to show surprise, interest, or mild admiration. In actual conversation, it often works as a quick listener response rather than a strong exclamation. Compared with "wow," it is

usually softer and closer to "oh, really?" or "is that so?" depending on the context.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

surprise

interest

backchannel response

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

backchannel expression

reaction expression

Hmm, I See

ふーん

Fuun

Hmm, I see.

Variants

- ふーん。
Hmm.
- ふうん。
I see.
- ふーん、そうなんだ。
Hmm, is that so?

Adjusted Expression

そうなんですね。

I see. Is that so?

Example

A 「その人、毎朝4時に起きるんだって」 B 「ふーん」

A: They say that person gets up at four every morning. B: Hmm, I see.

Notes

"Fuun" is an interjection used as an immediate listener response. It can show mild interest, acknowledgment, or emotional distance, depending on intonation and context. Unlike "hee," it often sounds flatter and may even suggest that the speaker is not especially impressed.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

reaction

interest

brushing off

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

backchannel expression

reaction expression

Oh, I See!

そっか！

Sokka!

Oh, I see!

Variants

- そうか。
Oh, I see.
- そっか。
I see now.
- そっか、なるほど。
Oh, right.

Adjusted Expression

そういうことなのですね。

I see. So that is how it is.

Example

A 「あした やす明日は休みだよ」 B 「そっか！」

A: Tomorrow is a holiday. B: Oh, I see!

Notes

"Sokka" is a colloquial contracted form of "sou ka." It is used when the speaker understands something, realizes something, or sees how a situation fits together. Compared with "hee," it shows not just surprise or

interest, but a sense that the information has now made sense to the speaker.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

understanding

realization

reaction

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

reaction expression

realization expression

So-So

まあまあ

Maamaa

So-so.

Variants

- まあまあだね。

So-so.

- まあ、悪^{わる}くないよ。

Not bad.

- そんなに悪^{わる}くなかったよ。

It was okay.

Adjusted Expression

とく^{とく}にすごく良^よかったわけではありませんが、悪^{わる}くもありませんでした。

It was not especially good, but it was not bad either.

Example

A 「試験^{しけん}、どうだった？」 B 「まあまあ、難^{むずか}しかったけど、なんとかできたよ。」

A: How was the exam? B: So-so. It was difficult, but I managed.

Notes

"Maamaa" is a common spoken expression used when the speaker gives a moderate or noncommittal evaluation. It often means that something

was neither especially good nor especially bad. Depending on tone and context, it can sound mildly positive, lukewarm, or slightly withholding.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

moderate evaluation

reaction

softened reply

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

evaluative expression

ambiguous reply

Oh, That's It?

な あ ん だ

Naanda

Oh, that's it?

Variants

- なんだ。
Oh, that's it?
- なーんだ。
Oh, I see.
- なんだ、そういうことか。
So that was it.

Adjusted Expression

そういうことだったのですね。

I see. So that was what it was.

Example

A 「リモコンが見つからないと思ったら、ソファの下にあった」 B 「なあん
だ、そんなところにあったのか」

A: I thought I had lost the remote, but it was under the sofa. B: Oh, that's
it? So it was there.

Notes

"Naanda" is an interjection used when something becomes clear and the speaker reacts with a sense of anticlimax, mild surprise, or relief. It often

comes out when the answer turns out to be simpler, smaller, or less serious than expected. Compared with "sokka," it more easily carries the feeling of "Oh, it was only that."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

realization

anticlimax

reaction

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

reaction expression

realization expression

Two thumbs up

いいね

Ii ne

Nice

Variants

- いいね。
That's good.
- いいですね。
Two thumbs up.
- それ、いいね。
That sounds good.

Adjusted Expression

それはよい^{おも}と思います。

I think that is good.

Example

A 「この店^{みせ}、行^いってみない？」 B 「いいね」

A: Why don't we try this place? B: Nice.

Notes

"Ii ne" is a common spoken expression used to show approval, agreement, or a favorable reaction on the spot. It can also be used as a translation of "Two thumbs up," which conveys a strong positive feeling.

The phrase is versatile and can be used in various contexts to express that you like something or agree with it.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

agreement

positive evaluation

shared feeling

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

evaluative expression

agreement expression

You're Kidding!

うそだあ～

Uso daa~

You're kidding!

Variants

- うそだあ。
You're kidding!
- うそでしょ？
No way!
- まさか！
You can't be serious!

Adjusted Expression

それはうそでしょう。

That cannot be true.

Example

A 「^{たなか}田中くんのお^{とう}父さんは^{ごじち}ゴジラなんだって」 B 「うそだあ～」

Notes

"Uso daa~" is a colloquial reaction used when the speaker hears something and responds with disbelief or surprise. Rather than calmly judging whether something is true, it sounds like a spontaneous reaction close to "Really?" or "You're kidding!"

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

disbelief

surprise

reaction

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

reaction expression

disbelief expression

Really?

ほんとうー

Hontoo

Really?

Variants

- ほんと？
Really?
- ほんとう？
Is that true?
- ほんとうー？
For real?

Adjusted Expression

ほんとう
本当ですか。

Is that really true?

Example

A 「その人、独学で10か国語できるんだって」 B 「ほんとうー」

A: They say that person taught themselves ten languages. B: Really?

Notes

"Hontoo" is a casual reaction used when the speaker shows surprise, interest, or mild disbelief. It is often lighter and softer than a strong expression of disbelief, and it can function as a quick listener response. When I was a child, my mother often said this to me, and I was happy to

hear it, so I would go to the library, learn something new, and tell it to her.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

surprise

interest

mild disbelief

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

reaction expression

backchannel expression

Thanks to You

おかげさまで

Okage-sama de

Thanks to you, I'm doing well.

Variants

- おかげさまで、^{げんき}元気です。
Thanks to you, I'm doing well.
- おかげさまで、なんとかやっています。
Thanks to your support, I'm doing fine.
- I'm doing well, thanks to you.

Adjusted Expression

皆さまのおかげで、元気に過ごしております。

Thanks to everyone's support, I have been doing well.

Example

A 「お^{げんき}元気ですか。」 B 「おかげさまで、^{げんき}元気です。」

A: How have you been? B: Thanks to you, I'm doing well.

Notes

"Okage-sama de" is a polite formulaic expression used to respond with gratitude, often when someone asks how you are doing. It does not simply mean "thanks," but carries the sense that one's present well-being

is due to the kindness, support, or consideration of others. Because of this, it does not map neatly onto a single fixed English phrase.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

gratitude

responding about one's condition

polite expression

Tags EN

formulaic expression

spoken

gratitude expression

greeting expression

Excuse Me for Leaving First

さき しつれい
お先に失礼します。

Osaki ni shitsurei shimasu.

Excuse me for leaving before you.

Variants

- お先に失礼します。

Excuse me for leaving first.

- お先に上がります。

I'll be leaving now.

- お先に失礼いたします。

Please excuse me for heading out before you.

Adjusted Expression

それでは、お先に失礼いたします。

Well then, please excuse me for leaving before you.

Example

それでは、お先に失礼します。

Well then, please excuse me for leaving before you.

Notes

"Osaki ni shitsurei shimasu" is a polite fixed expression used when the speaker leaves while others are still staying, especially in workplaces. It is not a general equivalent of "goodbye," but a more specific expression

meaning that the speaker is excusing themselves for leaving first. A related workplace expression is "otsukaresama desu/deshita," but that has a different function and nuance.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

leaving greeting polite expression

Tags EN

formulaic expression spoken workplace expression parting expression

Oh, I Didn't Know That

そうでしたか。

Sou deshita ka.

Oh, I didn't know that.

Variants

- そうだったんですか。
Oh, I didn't know that.
- そうですね。
I see.
- そうでしたか。
Oh, is that so?

Adjusted Expression

それは知りませんでした。

I did not know that.

Example

A 「先生、来週は休講です。」 B 「そうでしたか。」

A: The class will be canceled next week. B: Oh, I didn't know that.

Notes

"Sou deshita ka" is a polite reaction expression used when the speaker has just learned something new and responds with understanding, mild surprise, or acknowledgment. The past form gives it a reflective nuance,

as if the speaker is taking in what has just been explained. It is often softer and more polite than a casual response such as "sokka."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

understanding

realization

mild surprise

polite response

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

reaction expression

polite expression

I Can't Make Sense of It

なに なん
何が何だかわからない。

Nani ga nan da ka wakaranai.

I can't make sense of what's what.

Variants

- なに なん 何が何だかわからない。

I can't make sense of what's what.

- なに なん もう何が何だかわからない。

I have no idea what's going on.

- なに 何がどうなっているのかわからない。

I can't tell what's what anymore.

Adjusted Expression

じょうきょう ふくざつ 状況が複雑で、なに 何がどうなっているのか理解できません。

The situation is so complicated that I cannot understand what is going on.

Example

かれ 彼がせつめい 説明してくれるけど、はや あまりにも速すぎて、なに なん 何が何だかわからない。

He explains it to me, but he speaks so fast that I can't make sense of what's what.

Notes

"Nani ga nan da ka wakaranai" is used when the speaker feels confused and cannot sort out what is what in the situation. It often appears when too many things are happening at once, when an explanation is hard to follow, or when the speaker feels mentally overwhelmed. Rather than a calm statement of non-understanding, it often carries the feeling of immediate confusion.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

confusion

difficulty in understanding

failure to grasp the situation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

confusion expression

difficulty-understanding expression

I'll Give It a Try

やってみます。

Yatte mimasu.

I'll give it a try.

Variants

- やってみます。
I'll give it a try.
- ちょっとやってみます。
I'll try it.
- まずはやってみます。
I'll go ahead and try.

Adjusted Expression

まずは一度、試しにやってみます。

First, I will try doing it once and see how it goes.

Example

A 「この料理、^{りょうり}作^{つく}ってみる？」 B 「ええ、やってみます」

A: Do you want to try making this dish? B: Yes, I'll give it a try.

Notes

"Yatte mimasu" is used when the speaker expresses a willingness to try doing something. It often appears as a positive response to a suggestion, invitation, or challenge. Rather than guaranteeing success, it conveys a readiness to attempt something and see how it goes.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

trying

willingness

positive response

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

response expression

trial expression

Not Really

そうでもない

Sou demo nai

not really

Variants

- そうでもない
not really
- そうでもないよ
not that much
- べつにそうでもない
it's not really like that

Adjusted Expression

それほど^{たいへん}大変ではありません。

It is not that tough.

Example

A 「^{たいへん}大変だね」 B 「そうでもないよ」

A: That sounds tough. B: Not really.

Notes

"Sou demo nai" is used when the speaker responds by softening, downplaying, or gently denying what has just been said. It often appears when someone says something was hard, serious, great, or extreme, and

the speaker answers that it was not quite so. Depending on tone and context, it can sound modest, reassuring, reserved, or slightly bluffing.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

soft denial

modest response

downplaying a situation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

response expression

soft denial expression

Anyway / In Any Case

どちみち

Dochimichi

anyway / in any case

Variants

- どのみち
 anyway
- いずれにせよ
 in any case
- とにかく
 either way

Adjusted Expression

どのみち、結果は変わらないと思います。

In any case, I think the result will not change.

Example

A 「僕は宿題ぼく しゅくだいはしないつもりだ」 B 「そうだね、どちみち、単位たんい とは取れないだろう」

A: I don't plan to do my homework. B: Right, either way, you probably won't get the credits.

Notes

"Dochimichi" means "anyway," "either way," or "in any case." It is used when the speaker sees the outcome as essentially unchanged no matter

which course is taken. In conversation, it can carry a nuance of resignation, inevitability, or rough practical judgment. The form "donomichi" is also common and is often felt to be slightly more standard.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

stating the outcome

resignation

sorting out the situation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

conclusion-marking expression

outlook expression

In the End

けっきょく
結局

Kekkyoku

in the end

Variants

- ^{けっきょく}結局
in the end
- ^{けっきょく}結局のところ
after all
- ^{さいご}最後には
eventually

Adjusted Expression

^{さいしゅうでき}最終的には、彼が来ることになりました。

In the end, it was decided that he would come.

Example

A 「^{けっきょく}結局、^{かれ}彼が来ることになりました」

A: In the end, it was decided that he would come.

Notes

"Kekkyoku" is used when the speaker presents the final outcome after various possibilities, expectations, or developments. It often carries the

feeling that things turned out that way after all, sometimes with a nuance of summary, resignation, or practical conclusion.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

stating a conclusion

summing up a result

expression of outcome

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

conclusion-marking expression

result expression

There's Nothing We Can Do

どうにもならない。

Dou ni mo naranai.

There's nothing we can do.

Variants

- どうにもならない。
There's nothing we can do.
- もうどうにもならない。
There's nothing I can do.
- どうしようもない。
It can't be helped.

Adjusted Expression

この状況では、今のところどうすることもできません。

In this situation, there is nothing we can do for now.

Example

A 「^{あめ}雨が^ふ降っているから、^{せんたく}洗濯が^ほ干せない」 B 「こればかりは、どうにもならないね」

A: It's raining, so I can't hang out the laundry. B: In this case, there's nothing we can do.

Notes

"Dou ni mo naranai" is used when the speaker feels that the situation cannot be changed no matter what they do. It expresses helplessness,

resignation, or the sense that things are beyond one's control. In conversation, it often appears as an immediate reaction to an unpleasant but unavoidable situation. "kore bakari wa" can be added at the beginning to emphasize that this is a situation where nothing can be done.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

helplessness

resignation

accepting the situation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

expression of resignation

expression of helplessness

Ultimately / In the End

さいしゅうてき
最終的には

Saishuuteki ni wa

ultimately / in the end

Variants

- さいしゅうてき最終的には
ultimately
- けっきょく結局
in the end
- さいご最後には
after all

Adjusted Expression

さいしゅうてき はんだん最終的な判断としては、きそのように決まりました。

As the final decision, that is what was decided.

Example

さいしゅうてき「最終的には、さんせいみんな賛成しました。」

In the end, everyone agreed.

Notes

"Saishuuteki ni wa" is used when the speaker presents the final outcome after a process, discussion, or series of events. However, this expression by itself does not guarantee that everyone agreed willingly. In actual

situations, it may simply mean that a decision was reached, sometimes because someone with stronger influence pushed it through.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

stating a conclusion

summing up a result

expression of decision

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

conclusion-marking expression

result expression

Either Way

どちらにしても

Dochira ni shitemo

either way

Variants

- どちらにしても
either way
- どっちにしても
in any case
- いずれにしても
whichever way it goes

Adjusted Expression

いずれにしても、確認が必要です。

In any case, confirmation is necessary.

Example

「どちらにしても、かくにん ひつよう確認が必要です」

Either way, we need to confirm it.

Notes

"Dochira ni shitemo" is used when the speaker wants to say that the same point holds regardless of which option is chosen. It is useful for summarizing a discussion, narrowing the focus, or moving people away from unproductive back-and-forth. In meetings, for example, it can help

cut through a long and boring discussion by shifting attention to what still needs to be done anyway.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

sorting out the situation

stating a conclusion

bringing discussion to a close

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

conclusion-marking expression

discussion-organizing expression

Everyone's Doing Fine

みんな、^{げんき}元気してるよ。

Minna, genki shiteru yo.

Everyone's doing fine.

Variants

- みんな、^{げんき}元気してるよ。
Everyone's doing fine.
- みんな^{げんき}元気だよ。
Everyone's fine.
- みんな^{げんき}元気にしてるよ。
They're all doing well.

Adjusted Expression

みんな^{げんき}元気にしていますよ。

Everyone is doing well.

Example

A 「みんな、^{げんき}元気してる？」 B 「みんな、^{げんき}元気してるよ」

A: How's everyone doing? B: Everyone's doing fine.

Notes

"Minna, genki shiteru yo" is a casual way to say that everyone is doing well. It often appears as a response when someone asks about family

members, friends, or people back home. In some dialects, "shiteru" may appear as "shitoru," as in "genki shitoru?" or "genki shitoru yo."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

reporting how people are doing response reply to concern

Tags EN

spoken well-being expression response expression greeting-related expression

Either Way

いずれにせよ

Izure ni seyo

either way

Variants

- いずれにしても
either way
- どちらにしても
in any case
- ともかく
at any rate

Adjusted Expression

いずれにせよ、準備じゅんびをしておいたほうがよいおもと思います。

Either way, I think it is better to be prepared.

Example

A 「いずれにせよ、準備じゅんびをしておいたほうがいい」

A: Either way, it is better to be prepared.

Notes

"Izure ni seyo" is used when the speaker closes off several possible branches and moves on to what still holds. It does not decide which possibility is correct; it says that the next point applies regardless.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

closing off alternatives

moving the discussion forward

linking to a conclusion

Tags EN

formulaic expression

connective expression

explanatory expression

discourse expression

Oops!

おっと！

Otto!

Oops!

Variants

- おっと。
Oops!
- おっとっと。
Whoops!

Adjusted Expression

おっと、傘かさを持ってくるのを忘れていました。

Oops, I forgot to bring my umbrella.

Example

A 「おっと、傘かさ、持ってくるの、忘れてた」

A: Oops, I forgot to bring my umbrella.

Notes

"Otto" is an immediate reaction used when the speaker suddenly notices something: a small mistake, a missed item, a near slip, or an unexpected turn. It is not a carefully chosen sentence but a quick sound that appears at the moment of noticing.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

realization

reaction to a mistake

immediate reaction

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken expression

reaction expression

interjection

Wow!

わあ！

Waa!

Wow!

Variants

- わあ。

Wow!

- わあ、すごい！

Wow, that's amazing!

Adjusted Expression

わあ、すばらしいですね。

Wow, that is wonderful.

Example

A 「わあ、すごい！」

A: Wow, that's amazing!

Notes

"Waa" is an immediate reaction to something that appears before the speaker as surprising, impressive, beautiful, or larger than expected. The politeness is not carried by "waa" itself but by what follows, as in "Waa, that is wonderful."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

surprise

admiration

immediate reaction

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken expression

reaction expression

interjection

Adding "o" to "hazukashii" makes it polite?

失礼しました。これはこれは、お恥かしはずしい。

Shitsurei shimashita. Kore wa kore wa, ohazukashii.

I sincerely apologize. This is a serious failure on my part.

Variants

- これはこれは、お恥かしはずしい。

Well, this is embarrassing.

- お恥かしはずしいです。

How embarrassing.

Adjusted Expression

失礼しつれいいたしました。お恥はずかしいところをお見みせしてしまいました。

I sincerely apologize for having shown such a serious lapse on my part.

Example

A 「失礼しつれいしました。これはこれは、お恥はずかしい」

A: I sincerely apologize. This is a serious failure on my part.

Notes

It is rare to directly say the word "hazukashii," which means "embarrassing," in Japanese. However, when you make a trivial mistake or a minor error, you may say this phrase with a light apology such as "shitsurei shimashita," which means "I'm sorry." When you utter this

phrase, it is polite and has a relaxing effect on the conversation. If you can respond beautifully like this, no one will think of you as an "embarrassing person," but rather as a person with very worldly common sense.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

light apology

easing the atmosphere

reaction to a mistake

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

polite expression

interaction-adjusting expression

What a Relief

ほっとした。

Hotto shita.

What a relief.

Variants

- ほっとした。
What a relief.
- ほっとしました。
I'm relieved.
- ひとまず、ほっとした。
That's a relief.

Adjusted Expression

ひとまず、ほっとしました。

For now, that's a relief.

Example

A 「しけん試験、ぜんぶ全部、お終わって、ほっとした」

A: All the exams are over. What a relief.

Notes

The phrase "hotto shita" is used to express relief. It is used to indicate that something has ended or been resolved. However, is there really anything to be relieved about? When one exam is over, there is another exam. When you find out that a girl you had feelings for likes you too,

you may feel relieved at that moment, but after you find out that you both like each other, the excitement and tenderness you felt before may become weaker.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

relief release from tension reaction to an event

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken expression emotional expression reaction expression

Really?

ほんとう
本当ですかあ？

Hontou desu kaa?

Really?

Variants

- 本当ですか？
Really?
- ほんとうですか？
Is that true?
- 本当なの？
Are you sure?
- 本当？

Adjusted Expression

ほんとう
本当ですか。

Is that true?

Example

A 「あした明日、あめ雨がふ降るってい言ってたよ」 B 「ほんとう本当ですかあ？ はこんなには晴れているのに」

A: They said it will rain tomorrow. B: Really? But it's so sunny today.

Notes

"Hontou desu kaa?" is a reaction used when the speaker cannot immediately accept what someone has just said. It is not only a request for confirmation; it also carries surprise or slight doubt. The lengthened "kaa" makes the reaction sound more unexpected than a plain "Hontou desu ka?" For formal confirmation, it is better not to stretch the ending.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

surprise

doubt

confirmation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

reaction expression

confirmation expression

I'm not so sure.

そうかなあ？ 【^{なっとく}納得いかないけど】

Sou kanaa? (Nattoku ikanai kedo)

I'm not so sure. (I'm not convinced.)

Variants

- そうかなあ？

I'm not so sure.

- そうですかね。

Really?

- そうかな。

I wonder about that.

- そうかなあ。

I'm not convinced.

Adjusted Expression

そうでしょうか。 ^{わたし}私は ^{ちが}少し ^{おも}違うと思います。

I'm not sure that is right. I see it a little differently.

Example

A 「これ、おいしいね」 B 「そうかなあ？ 私はあまりそう思わないけど」

A: This is delicious. B: I'm not so sure. I don't really think so.

Notes

"Sou kanaa?" is used when you cannot immediately agree with what someone has said. It is not a strong denial, but it does show that you are not convinced. When you disagree with someone, strongly saying no right away is not always wise. But saying "yes" when you do not agree is not a good idea either, because you may sound like a person who agrees with everything. In that kind of situation, saying "sou kanaa" quietly lets you show a little doubt without breaking the relationship.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

doubt

disagreement

soft disagreement

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

disagreement expression

reaction expression

Yay!

やったあ！

Yattaa!

Yay!

Variants

- やった！
Yay!
- やりました！
I did it!
- We made it!

Adjusted Expression

やりました。

I did it.

Example

A 「しけん試験、ごうかく合格したよ」 B 「やったあ！」

A: I passed the exam. B: Yay!

Notes

"Yattaa" is a joyful reaction used when something has gone well or when you hear good news. You can use it for your own success, and you can also use it when sharing someone else's happiness. Because it is a spoken expression of joy, the situation matters. If you say it loudly or too often,

you may sound too eager to show your feelings. Also, when you are happy, someone nearby may not be in a position to celebrate in the same way.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

achievement joy reaction to success

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken reaction expression emotional expression

That's not fair!

それはないでしょう！

sorewanai deshou!

That's not fair!

Variants

- それはないでしょう！
That's not fair!
- それはないよ。
Come on, that's not right.
- それはひどいよ。
That's too much!

Adjusted Expression

それは少しひどいと思います。

I think that's a bit unfair.

Example

A 「お菓子、全部、食べちゃった」 B 「それはないでしょう！」

A: I ate all the sweets. B: That's not fair!

Notes

The phrase "sorewanai deshou" is used to express unfairness or injustice. It is used to raise your voice to express dissatisfaction or objection. If you use this expression too much, people around you may think you are always dissatisfied.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

dissatisfaction

objection

reaction to unfairness

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

disagreement expression

reaction expression

It helps me a lot!

ほんとう たす
本当に助かります！

hontouni tasukarimasu!

It helps me a lot!

Variants

- 助かります。
That really helps me.
- 本当に助かりました。
That helped me a lot.

Adjusted Expression

たいへんたす
大変助かります。

That is very helpful.

Example

A 「^{てつだ}手伝いましょうか？」 B 「^{ほんとう たす}本当に助かります！」

A: Can I help you? B: That really helps me!

Notes

The phrase "hontouni tasukarimasu" is used to express gratitude when someone will do or has done something for you.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

gratitude relief reaction to help

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

gratitude expression

reaction expression

Sorry I couldn't do it well.

ごめんね、うまくできなくて。

Gomen ne, umaku dekinakute.

I'm sorry I couldn't do it well.

Variants

- ごめんね、うまくできなくて。
I'm sorry I couldn't do it well.
- ごめん、うまくできなくて。
Sorry I messed it up.
- ごめんなさい、うまくできなくて。
I'm sorry it didn't turn out well.

Adjusted Expression

もう わけ
申し訳ありません、うまくできなくて。

I'm sorry I wasn't able to do it well.

Example

A 「りょうり料理、しっぱい失敗しちゃった。ごめんね、うまくできなくて」

A: I messed up the cooking. I'm sorry I couldn't do it well.

Notes

The phrase "gomen ne, umaku dekinakute" is used to express an apology for not being able to do something well.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

apology reaction to failure soft expression

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken apology expression failure expression

Hobbies

しゅみ なん
趣味は何ですか？

Shumi wa nan desu ka?

What is your hobby?

Variants

- 趣味は何ですか？
What is your hobby?
- ご趣味は何ですか？
What are your hobbies?

Adjusted Expression

しゅみ なん
ご趣味は何ですか？

What are your hobbies?

Example

A 「しゅみ なん 趣味は何ですか？」 B 「おんがく き 音楽を聴くことです」

A: What is your hobby? B: Listening to music.

Notes

The phrase "shumi wa nan desu ka?" is used to ask someone what their hobby is.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

question

starting a conversation

interest in the other person

Tags EN

formulaic expression

spoken

question expression

conversation expression

How about it?

いかがですか？

Ikaga desu ka?

How about it?

Variants

- いかがですか？
How about it?
- いかがでしょうか？
Would you like it?
- What do you think?

Adjusted Expression

いかがでしょうか？

Would you like it?

Example

A 「たなかせんせい田中先生、わたし私は、たこれを食べてみたいのですが、せんせい先生もいかがですか？」

A: Professor Tanaka, I would like to try this. How about you?

Notes

The phrase "ikagadesuka?" is used to suggest something to someone. It is a polite expression that is often used when you want to propose something to someone. In Japanese, it is generally considered rude to ask someone's feelings or intentions without using honorific language.

However, since there are various forms of honorific language, it is troublesome to remember or pronounce them. Therefore, if you express your intentions in advance and then say "ikagadesuka?", you can ask politely without using honorific language.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

suggestion

offering

polite inquiry

Tags EN

formulaic expression

spoken

suggestion expression

polite expression

Is that so?

そうなんですか？

Sounandesuka?

Is that so?

Variants

- そうなんですか？
Is that so?
- そうなんですか。
Really?
- そうなんですね。
Oh, is that so?

Adjusted Expression

そうなのですか？

Is that so?

Example

A 「うちの子、もう^{ことし}今年、^{しょうがっこう}小学校に^{にゅうがく}入学するんですよ」 B 「そうなんですか？」

A: My child is entering elementary school this year. B: Is that so?

Notes

The phrase "sounandesuka?" is used as an interjection to express surprise or doubt. It is used not so much to confirm whether something is true, but to show a little surprise and to express that you have received

the information with interest or even joy. On the other hand, when expressing doubt, raise the end of the phrase and pronounce it a little longer. The meaning changes significantly depending on how you pronounce it.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

surprise

backchannel response

doubt

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

reaction expression

backchannel expression

That's it!

ええ、それです。

Ee, sore desu.

That's it!

Variants

- ええ、それです。

That's it!

- あ、それです。

Yes, that's it.

- それぞれ。

That's the one.

Adjusted Expression

ええ、それが^{せいかい}正解です。

Yes, that's the correct answer.

Example

A 「^{きのう}昨日行^いったカ^かフ^ふエの名^な前^{まえ}、何^{なん}だ^だっ^った^っけ？」 B 「^{ぶるー}ブルー^ーじゃ^なか^った？」

A 「ええ、それです！」

A: What was the name of the cafe we went to yesterday? B: Wasn't it Blue? A: That's it!

Notes

The phrase "ee, sore desu" is used to agree when someone tells you the answer to something you cannot remember. It can also be used when

someone finds what you were looking for and you acknowledge that it is indeed what you were looking for. It is a combination of simple words such as "ee," "sore," and "desu," but if you do not observe Japanese conversations well, you may not realize that you can express it with such simple words. Such expressions are called idioms. If you can use idioms, you can naturally learn how to speak.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

confirmation

agreement

successful recall

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

confirmation expression

reaction expression

Better that way

その^{ほう}方が...

Sono hou ga...

That might be better...

Variants

- その^{ほう}方が...
That might be better...
- そうした^{ほう}方が...
It may be better that way...
- その^{ほう}方がいいかもね。
Maybe that's the better option...

Adjusted Expression

そうした方がよいと思います。

I think it would be better that way.

Example

A 「やっぱり、^{ぜんぶてきぎょう}全部手作業でやります」 B 「ええ、たしかに^{じかん}時間はかかるけど、その^{ほう}方が...」

A: I'll do it all by hand after all. B: Yes, it certainly takes time, but that might be better...

Notes

The phrase "sono hou ga..." is an expression that suggests something might be better, even if it is not the perfect choice. If you say it without leaving it unfinished, it would mean something like "It may be better to do it that way," but ending the sentence midway shows a willingness to respect the other person's decision without explicitly stating everything. This subtlety creates politeness and consideration.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

suggestion

indirect advice

consideration

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

indirect expression

considerate expression

elliptical expression

What a waste.

もったいない。

mottainai.

What a waste.

Variants

- もったいない。

What a waste.

- じかん時間^{じかん}がもったいない。

That's a waste of time.

- それはもったいない。

It would be a waste.

Adjusted Expression

それは無駄^{むだ}になってしまうので、もったいないです。

That would be a waste, so it would be better not to do that.

Example

A 「けいたい携帯^{けいたい}を見ていたのでは、じかん時間^{じかん}がもったいないので、しゅくだい宿題^{しゅくだい}をしてしまいました
よう」

A: If we keep looking at our phones, it will be a waste of time, so let's get our homework done.

Notes

The phrase "mottainai" is used to express regret or disappointment that something is wasted. It is used to indicate that something is wasted or not

used effectively. It is often used when you see someone throwing away food or when you see someone not using something that is still useful. It is also used when you see someone not using their abilities effectively.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

reaction to waste

regret

warning

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

reaction expression

value-judgment expression

Long time no see!

ひさ
お久しぶりです。

Ohisashiburi desu.

Long time no see!

Variants

- お^{ひさ}久しぶりです。

Long time no see!

- お^{ひさ}久しぶりですね。

It's been a while.

- ご^{ぶさ}無^さ汰^たしております。

I haven't seen you in a long time.

Adjusted Expression

ご^{ぶさ}無^さ汰^たしております。

It has been a long time since we last met.

Example

A 「お^{ひさ}久しぶりですね」

A: Long time no see!

Notes

The phrase "ohisashiburi desu" is a polite expression used when you meet someone you have not seen in a long time. It can be used when you

meet a friend you have not seen since you graduated from school, or a colleague you have not seen since you changed jobs.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

greeting on meeting again

polite opening

expression of familiarity

Tags EN

formulaic expression

spoken

greeting expression

reunion expression

Thank you for taking care of me!

せ わ
お世話になりました。

Osewa ni narimashita.

Thank you for taking care of me!

Variants

- お世話になりました。
Thank you for taking care of me.
- いろいろお世話になりました。
Thank you for all your help.
- 大変お世話になりました。
Thank you very much for your support.

Adjusted Expression

大変お世話になりました。

Thank you very much for all your support.

Example

A 「^{きょう}今日は、お^{せ わ}世話になりました」

A: Thank you for taking care of me today.

Notes

The phrase "osewa ni narimashita" is a polite expression used to express gratitude for the care and support you have received.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

gratitude parting greeting polite expression

Tags EN

formulaic expression spoken gratitude expression greeting expression

I came here from far away.

はるばる き
遥々やって来ました。

Harubaru yatte kimashita.

I came here from far away.

Variants

- はるばる き
遥々やって来ました。

I came here from far away.

- はるばる き
遥々来ました。

I came all the way here.

- とお き
遠くから来ました。

I came from a long way away.

Adjusted Expression

えんぼう まい
遠方から参りました。

I have come from far away.

Example

A 「はるばる き
遥々やって来ました」

A: I came here from far away.

Notes

The phrase "harubaru yatte kimashita" is used to express that you have come from a long distance. The point is to use "yatte" before "kimashita" to express that you have come from far away. When you use this

expression after coming from a place that is not so far away, it will naturally be taken as ironic.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

arrival from far away

emphasis on distance

light greeting

Tags EN

lexical expression

spoken

arrival expression

emphatic expression

By chance

たまたまですよ。

Tamatama desu yo.

It's just a coincidence.

Variants

- たまたまですよ。
It's just a coincidence.
- たまたまです。
It just happened that way.
- たまたまうまくいっただけです。
I just happened to do well this time.

Adjusted Expression

たまたまうまくいっただけです。

I just happened to do well this time.

Example

A 「試験^{しけん}、いい点数^{てんすう}がとれましたね」 B 「たまたまですよ」

A: You got a good score on the exam. B: It's just a coincidence.

Notes

The phrase "tamatama desu yo" is used to express that something happened by chance. However, as in this example, when you are praised for something, you can show a humble attitude by saying that it happened by chance, even if it was actually the result of your effort. It is

perfectly fine to think in your heart that the result really came from your own ability and effort.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

explaining chance

humility

response to praise

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

humility expression

response expression

After a little while

ちよつと^お落ち^っ着いてから

Chotto ochitsuite kara

After a little while

Variants

- ちよつと^お落ち^っ着いてから

After a little while

- 少し^お落ち^っ着いてから

After I settle down a bit

- ちよつとしてから

After a short while

Adjusted Expression

^{すこ}少し^お落ち^っ着いてからにしましょう。

Let's do it after I settle down a little.

Example

A 「すぐに^た食べ^ましょうか？」 B 「いえ、ちよつと^お落ち^っ着いてから...」

A: Shall we eat right away? B: No, after I settle down a bit first...

Notes

The phrase "chotto ochitsuite kara" is used when you want to take a break after returning from going out. It can be used when you want to take a break after returning from going out, such as changing clothes,

organizing your belongings, or taking a break. If you simply say "I want to take a break," the person you are talking to may want to know the reason or time you want to take a break.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

asking for a little time

soft postponement

adjusting the situation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

postponement expression

interaction-adjusting expression

One thing at a time

ひとつずつ

Hitotsuzutsu

One thing at a time

Variants

- ひとつずつ

One thing at a time

- ひと一つずつ

One by one

- ひと ひと一つ一つ

One at a time

Adjusted Expression

ひとつずつ^{かくにん}確認しながら、片付けて^{かたづ}いきます。

I will deal with them one by one while checking each one carefully.

Example

A 「何か^{なに}手伝^{てつだ}いましょうか？」 B 「いえ、大丈夫^{だいじょうぶ}です。ひとつずつ、片付けて^{かたづ}いきます」

A: Can I help you with something? B: No, I'm fine. I will clean things up one thing at a time.

Notes

The phrase "hitotsuzutsu" is used to express that you are doing things one by one. Doing things one by one is a basic idea in situations such as

cleaning up a room, organizing your belongings, or carrying out work. When you say you do things one by one, it may also include the meaning of checking each one and doing it carefully and reliably.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

step-by-step handling

showing reassurance

stating a way of proceeding

Tags EN

lexical expression

spoken

order expression

work expression

Do you want something?

なに ほ
何か欲しいもの、ある？

Nanika hoshii mono, aru?

Do you want something?

Variants

- なに ほ 何か欲しいもの、ある？
Do you want something?
- 何かいる？
Do you need something?
- ほ 欲しいものある？
Is there anything you want?

Adjusted Expression

なに ほ
何か欲しいものがありますか？

Is there anything you would like?

Example

A 「なに ほ 何か欲しいもの、ある？」 B 「いえ、だいじょうぶです」

A: Do you want something? B: No, I'm fine.

Notes

The phrase "nanika hoshii mono aru?" is used when you want to ask if someone wants something, such as food, drink, or a gift. Please note that it is "nanika" not "nani ga".

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

offering

consideration

confirmation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

considerate expression

offering expression

Wanna go see it?

み い
見に行く？

Mi ni iku?

Wanna go see it?

Variants

- 見に行く？

Wanna go see it?

- 映画、見に行く？

Wanna go see a movie?

- 見に行かない？

Do you want to go see it?

Adjusted Expression

み い
見に行きませんか？

Would you like to go see it?

Example

A 「映画、見に行く？」 B 「うん、行く」

A: Wanna go see a movie? B: Yeah, I do.

Notes

The phrase "mi ni iku?" uses the particle "ni" to express the purpose of the action. Before the particle "ni," a noun or the continuative form of a verb is used. This expression can work both as an invitation and as a way

of asking about someone's plans. Because it is not a fully explicit invitation, it is convenient. If you want to invite someone more politely, you can say "mi ni ikimase ka?". However, if you are refused, it may feel awkward, so it is better not to use it unless you are fairly confident. An intermediate question like "mi ni iku?" lets you change your next move depending on the other person's reaction. If the other person says, "I'm not going," you can answer, "I am," and it becomes a question about plans rather than a direct invitation.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

invitation

checking plans

prompting

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

invitation expression

plan-checking expression

Let's go!

い
行こう！

Ikou!

Let's go!

Variants

- 行こう！
Let's go!
- 食べに行こう！
Let's go eat!
- 飲みに行こう！
Let's go for a drink!

Adjusted Expression

行きましょう

Shall we go?

Example

A 「食べに行こう！」 B 「いいね！」

A: Let's go eat! B: Sounds good!

Notes

The phrase "ikou!" is used to invite someone to go somewhere. In actual pronunciation, the "u" in "ikou" is not pronounced very strongly. Therefore, it may sound like "iko". Also, the "ni" in "tabeni" is not

pronounced strongly, so it may sound like "tabeiko". Similarly, expressions such as "nomiiko (let's go for a drink)," "miiko (let's go see it)," and "shiiko (let's go do it)" are often pronounced very simply, so it may be good to get used to it. It is certainly easy to pronounce it shortly, isn't it?

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

invitation

prompting

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

invitation expression

It's muggy

あつ
むし暑い

Mushiatsui

It's muggy

Variants

- むし暑い
It's muggy.
- 蒸し暑い
It's hot and humid.
- 今日はむし暑いね
It's really muggy today.

Adjusted Expression

(今日は)、^{きおん たか}気温が高く、^{しつど たか}湿度も高いですね。

It is hot and humid today.

Example

A 「むし^{あつ}暑いね」 B 「うん、暑^{あつ}いね」

A: It's muggy. B: Yeah, it's hot.

Notes

The phrase "mushiatsui" is a common expression in Japan, often used on hot and humid days. This expression is a compound of "mushi" and "atsui." "Mushi" refers to humidity, and "atsui" means "hot." Since people

can manage daily life without using such compound expressions, they can be difficult to master. Unless you consciously try to use them, you may not acquire them easily. However, if you can use them, your speech becomes clearer and more suitable for the situation.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

sharing the weather or physical feeling

expressing uncomfortable heat

seasonal conversation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

weather expression

physical sensation expression

compound word

summer

Don't mix them, it's dangerous!

まぜるな、^{きけん}危険！

Mazeruna, kiken!

Don't mix them, it's dangerous!

Variants

- まぜるな危険
Don't mix them, it's dangerous!
- 混ぜるな危険
What a dangerous combination!
- それ、まぜるな危険じゃん
Don't mix those!

Adjusted Expression

(それら)^{こんごう}を混合すると、^{きけん}危険である。

Mixing them is dangerous.

Example

A 「^{ひょうはくざい}漂白剤と^{せんざい}洗剤を^ま混ぜたら、^{きけん}危険ですよ」 B 「えっ、それ、まぜるな、^{きけん}危険じゃん」

A: If you mix bleach and detergent, it's dangerous. B: What? That's a dangerous combination! Don't mix them!

Notes

The phrase "mazeruna, kiken!" is used to warn that mixing certain things is dangerous. It is commonly used when telling someone not to combine things that should not be mixed. Bottles of chlorine bleach often have warnings like "Do not mix" on them. This phrase is also used humorously, for example, when two things make a striking or risky combination: "What? That combination is dangerous! Don't mix them!"

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

warning of danger

calling attention

emphatic expression used humorously

Tags EN

immediate grammar

formulaic expression

colloquial

warning expression

caution

humor

The first impression

だいいちいんしょう
第一印象

Daiichiinshou

The first impression

Variants

- 第一印象
the first impression
- 第一印象がいい
make a good first impression
- 第一印象では
at first impression

Adjusted Expression

さいしょ う いんしょう ごみばこ
最初に受けた印象は、ゴミ箱がないということだった。

My initial impression was that there were no trash cans.

Example

A 「日本はとうですか」 B 「ゴミ箱がないというのが第一印象ですね」

A: How is Japan? B: My first impression was that there are no trash cans.

Notes

The phrase "daiichiinshou" is a compound word formed from "daiichi" and "inshou." In this case, you can also say "daiichi no inshou," but not all combinations of words are used as compounds. For example, there is no

commonly used word like "daiinshou" ("second impression"), so you need to say "nibanme no inshou." Grammar can be helpful, but rules do not apply in all cases, so it is better to use expressions that are actually used.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing an initial impression

sharing a first evaluation

describing the beginning of an experience

Tags EN

immediate grammar

noun

compound word

evaluative expression

describing experience

Don't push yourself

むり
無理はしない

Muri wa shinai

Don't push yourself

Variants

- 無理はしない
Don't push yourself
- 無理しない
Don't overdo it
- 無理はしないで
Take it easy

Adjusted Expression

たいちょう わる
体調が悪いのだから、むり
無理をしないほうがよい。

Since you are not feeling well, you should not overexert yourself.

Example

A 「明日、あした しけん
試験があるけれども、ねつ
熱があるんだから、むり
無理はしない」

A: You have an exam tomorrow, but since you have a fever, don't push yourself.

Notes

The word "muri" refers to situations where you try to do something beyond your capacity. For example, studying for an exam without taking

proper rest when you are sick, or trying to treat a girl when you do not have enough money.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

showing concern for someone

telling someone not to overdo it

showing consideration for someone's condition or situation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

considerate expression

advice

health

concern

I want to relax.

のんびりしたいね。

Nonbirishitai ne.

I want to relax.

Variants

- のんびりしたいね。
I want to relax.
- 今日のはのんびりしたいね。
I want to take it easy today.
- 何もしないでのんびりしたいね。
I just want to relax and do nothing today.

Adjusted Expression

すこ少しゆっくりしたいですね。

I'd like to relax a little.

Example

A 「きょう今日は、なに何もしないで、のんびりしたいね」

A: I just want to relax and do nothing today.

Notes

The word "nonbiri" is an adverb that expresses a relaxed and leisurely state. It is used before a verb to describe doing something in a relaxed way. It can be used in expressions such as "nonbiri suru (to relax),"

"nonbiri shitai (want to relax)," "nonbiri shiyō (let's relax)," and
"nonbiri kurasu (to live a leisurely life)."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

sharing a feeling

sharing a wish

expression of relaxation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

expression of desire

expression of relaxation

Crowded trains are tough.

まんいでんしゃ つら
満員電車は辛い

Man'in densha wa tsurai.

Crowded trains are tough.

Variants

- 満員電車は辛い
Crowded trains are tough.
- 満員電車、辛いよね
Crowded trains are really tough.
- 満員電車は本当に辛い
Rush hour trains are tough.

Adjusted Expression

満員電車は大変ですね。

Crowded trains are difficult, aren't they?

Example

A 「まんいでんしゃ つら満員電車は辛い」

A: Crowded trains are tough.

Notes

The expression "man'in densha" is a compound made from "man'in" (full) and "densha" (train), referring to a crowded train. The adjective "tsurai" expresses a physically or emotionally difficult situation. It is often used to

describe something that is hard to endure, such as "tsurai shigoto" (a tough job) or "tsurai jikan" (a difficult time).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing evaluation

sharing empathy

expressing discomfort

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

expression of evaluation

expression of discomfort

Sort of...

まあ、なんとなく。

Maa nantonaku.

Well, sort of.

Variants

- まあ、なんとなく。
Well, sort of.
- なんとなく。
Sort of.
- まあ、なんかそんな感じ。
Well, kind of.

Adjusted Expression

とく りゆう
特に理由はないんですが、なんとなくそうおもいます。

I don't have a clear reason, but I kind of feel that way.

Example

A 「何か^{なに}食べ^たたいな」 B 「じゃあ、何か^{なに}食^たべる？」 A 「カレーライス？」 B
「なぜ？」 A 「まあ、なんとなく」

A: I want to eat something. B: Then, do you want to eat? A: Curry rice? B:
Why? A: Well, sort of.

Notes

The phrase "maa nantonaku" is used when you do not have a clear reason for something. It is often used when you cannot explain why even

if you are asked. It is more natural to say "nantonaku" briefly than to give a full explanation like "I feel that way." Other expressions include "maa, nantonaku wakarimasu" (Well, I kind of understand), "maa, nantonaku sou omoimasu" (Well, I kind of think so), and "maa, nantonaku sonna ki ga suru" (Well, I kind of feel that way).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

avoiding giving a reason

vague response

expressing a feeling

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

vague expression

response expression

What the heck!

なんてこった。

Nante kotta.

What the heck!

Variants

- なんてこった。
What the heck!
- なんてこったよ。
What on earth!
- なんてことだ。
What the hell!

Adjusted Expression

それは大変ですね。

That sounds serious.

Example

A 「昨日、急にパソコンが壊れちゃって、データが全部消えたんだ」 B 「なんてこった！修理できるの？」

A: Yesterday, my computer suddenly broke down and all the data disappeared. B: What the heck! Can it be repaired?

Notes

The phrase "nante kotta" expresses surprise or confusion. It is used when something unexpected happens, especially in troublesome situations. It

can sometimes be used for positive surprises as well, but it is more commonly associated with trouble or shock.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing surprise

expressing confusion

exclamation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

exclamatory expression

That's not true.

そんなことない

Sonna koto nai.

That's not true.

Variants

- そんなことない
That's not true.
- そんなことないよ
No, that's not true.
- そんなことないって
That's not the case.

Adjusted Expression

そんなことはありません。

That's not the case.

Example

A 「今日のプレゼン、うまくいかなかった気がする。」 B 「そんなことない、ちゃんと伝わってたよ」

A: I don't think today's presentation went well. B: That's not true, it came across well.

Notes

The phrase "sonna koto nai" is used to deny what the other person has said, often to encourage them. It is commonly used when someone

downplays their own performance or ability, and the speaker responds by rejecting that negative evaluation.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

denial encouragement rejecting an evaluation

Tags EN

immediate grammar spoken expression of denial expression of encouragement

I knew it.

やっぱり

Yappari.

I knew it.

Variants

- やっぱり
I knew it.
- やっぱりね
See?
- やっぱりそうか
Just as I thought.

Adjusted Expression

やはりそうですね。

That is as expected.

Example

A 「^{あめ}雨が^ふ降ってきた」 B 「やっぱり」

A: It's raining. B: I knew it.

Notes

The phrase "yappari" is used when something turns out as expected. It often expresses the speaker's feeling of confirmation or realization when what they anticipated actually happens.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

confirming an expectation

showing realization

light agreement

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

reaction expression

I see.

なるほど

Naruhodo.

I see.

Variants

- なるほど

I see.

- なるほどね

That makes sense.

- なるほどなるほど

I see, I see.

Adjusted Expression

なるほど、そういうことですね。

I see, that's what you mean.

Example

A 「最近、^{さいきん}趣味^{しゅみ}で絵^えを描^かき始^{はじ}めたんだ」 B 「なるほど、それでいつも^{たの}楽しそうなんだ」

A: I recently started drawing pictures as a hobby. B: I see, that's why you always look happy.

Notes

The phrase "naruhodo" is used to express that you understand the other person's explanation. It is used after hearing a specific explanation from

the other person. It is a natural expression that can be used even in short conversations. However, just because someone uses this expression does not necessarily mean that they really understand. Some of my former students used this expression even when they did not actually understand. Still, that does not mean it was meaningless. Even without full understanding, they may have been using "naruhodo naruhodo" as a strategy to encourage the other person to continue speaking. In that sense, it may have functioned as a strategy for promoting smooth conversation.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

- showing understanding
- showing agreement
- promoting conversation

Tags EN

- immediate grammar
- spoken
- backchannel expression
- conversation strategy

Take care

き
気をつけて

Ki o tsukete.

Take care.

Variants

- 気をつけて
Take care.
- 気をつけてね
Be careful.
- 帰り道、気をつけてね
Take care on your way home.

Adjusted Expression

き かえ
お気をつけてお帰りください。

Please take care on your way home.

Example

A 「^{かえ}帰り道、^{みち}気をつけてね」

A: Take care on your way home.

Notes

The phrase "ki o tsukete" is used to tell someone to be careful. It often expresses concern or care for the other person, especially when they are leaving or about to do something that may involve some risk.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

urging caution

showing care

parting expression

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

expression of care

I'm hooked.

はまっちゃった

Hamacchatta.

I'm hooked.

Variants

- はまっちゃった
I'm hooked.
- 最近、はまっちゃった
I've gotten hooked on it.
- すっかりはまっちゃった
I'm really into it.

Adjusted Expression

最近、それに夢中になっています。

I've recently become really interested in it.

Example

A 「最近、^{さいきん}漫画^{まんが}にはまっちゃった」

A: I've gotten hooked on manga recently.

Notes

The phrase "hamacchatta" is used to express that you have become really into something, such as a hobby, game, or TV show. It often has a casual and lively feeling.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing enthusiasm

sharing a recent state

expressing a feeling

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

expression of being into something

I'm back.

ただいま

Tadaima.

I'm back.

Variants

- ただいま
I'm back.
- ただいまー
I'm home.

Adjusted Expression

ただいま戻りました。

I have just returned.

Example

A 「ただいま」 B 「おかえり」

A: I'm back. B: Welcome back.

Notes

The phrase "tadaima" is used when you return home or to your workplace. However, "tadaima" has two meanings. One is the greeting in the example above, and the other is "right now" or "at this moment," as in "I will do it right now." The intonation is slightly different. In the latter meaning, the "da" is pronounced a little higher.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

returning greeting

announcing one's return

Tags EN

immediate grammar

spoken

greeting expression

polysemous expression

Colophon

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